

MTU2009) and 5 levels of P (0, 17.5, 26.2, 35.0, and 43.7 kg/ha) applied basally as superphosphate. Before last puddling, 26.8 kg K₂O/ha was applied basally and 120 kg N/ha was applied in equal splits: basal, topdressing 25 d after planting, and before panicle initiation.

Grain and straw yields were statistical-

ly analyzed (see table). All treatments with added P gave higher grain yield than the control. Highest mean grain yield (5.3 t/ha) was from IR50, which was significantly superior to all other varieties (see table).

Mean grain yield for different P levels was significant only to 26.2 kg P/ha.

MTU6910 yielded more straw than all other varieties (see table). Varieties which recorded higher grain yield recorded low straw yield.

IR50 was best for rabi and application of 26.2 kg P/ha appeared to produce maximum yield for most rabi varieties. □

Optimum seeding rate and nitrogen level for rice grown in semidry conditions

J. Krishnarajan, P. Muthukrishnan, and K. K. Subbiah, Agricultural College and Research Institute (ACRI), Madurai 625104, Tamil Nadu, India

In Tamil Nadu almost 200,000 ha of semidry land is planted to rice. We sought to identify optimum seeding rate and nitrogen level for rice grown in semidry land in field trials at ACRI in 1978-79 and 1979-80.

Five seeding rates — 60, 80, 100, 120, and 140 kg seed/ha — and 4 nitrogen

levels — 0, 40, 80, and 120 kg N/ha — were evaluated in a split-plot design with 3 replications. Soil was sandy with pH 7.6, medium levels of available N and P, and low K.

Dry seed of MDU1, a 135-d variety recommended by Tamil Nadu Agricultural University for semidry conditions, was sown in lines and N was applied in 2 equal splits: at maximum tillering (25 d after transplanting) and at panicle initiation. The crop was grown under controlled water conditions until tillering, then irrigated like lowland rice. Butachlor 5% granules were applied at 1.5 kg

ai/ha 5 d after sowing to control weeds.

Data on grain yield and other components are in the table. Seeding rate did not significantly influence grain yield in 1978-79. In 1979-80 sowing, 100 kg seed/ha produced the highest yield — 1.8 t/ha. There was no significant difference between 80 kg and 100 kg seed/ha, however.

Nitrogen level increased grain yield significantly at the no-N vs N application level, but there was no significant difference between applications of 40, 80, and 120 kg. The most economic dose was 40 kg N/ha. □

Effect of seeding rate and nitrogen level on grain yield and yield components, Tamil Nadu, 1978-1980.

Treatment	1978-79				1979-80			
	Productive tillers (no.)	Grains/panicle	1,000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers (no.)	Grains/panicle	1,000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Seeding rate (kg/ha)</i>								
60	5.5	64.4	21.2	0.7	6.3	66.4	21.2	1.2
80	5.8	63.8	21.3	1.0	6.6	69.0	21.8	1.6
100	5.5	58.7	21.2	0.9	6.3	59.5	20.8	1.8
120	4.9	52.5	20.8	0.6	5.3	51.4	20.4	1.0
140	5.3	56.2	20.9	0.7	5.7	55.2	21.2	1.1
<i>Nitrogen level (kg/ha)</i>								
0	4.1	53.9	20.8	0.6	4.4	58.3	20.8	0.8
40	6.4	58.7	20.8	0.8	7.1	59.2	20.8	1.5
80	5.6	61.8	21.2	0.9	6.3	62.3	21.5	1.6
120	5.4	62.3	21.4	0.9	6.2	61.4	21.6	1.5
SE								
Seeding rate	0.4	7.5	0.83	1.4	0.41	5.6	0.23	173
Nitrogen level	0.2	4.8	0.2	0.32	3.5	0.12	0.1	
CD (0.05)								
Seeding rate	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.4
Nitrogen level	0.5	ns	ns	0.2	0.65	ns	0.24	0.3

Effect of calcium peroxide-coated rice seeds on germination and seedling growth under submerged conditions

C. Kundu and S. Biswas, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, Hooghly, India

Rice is direct seeded in rainfed lowlands in much of Asia and South Asia. Sudden heavy rain often submerges the seeded fields, and greatly affects germination and seedling emergence.

We studied the effect of coating rice

seeds with calcium peroxide on germination and seedling establishment under submerged conditions. NC492 and Jaladhi 2 seeds were coated with 20% and 40% calcium peroxide by weight. Five seeds were sown in each 6-cm-diam